

Thermodynamics of Non-electrolyte Solutions. II. Excess Volumes of Binary Solutions of 2,2,4-Trimethylpentane with some Aromatic Compounds at 40°

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Manuscript received 19 June 1984, revised 9 September 1985, accepted 17 January 1986

Excess volumes of seven binary systems, viz 2,2,4-trimethylpentane + benzene; + toluene; + *o*-xylene; + *m*-xylene; + chlorobenzene; + benzaldehyde; and + acetophenone, have been determined at 40° over the entire range of composition by using a bicapillary pycnometer. The results have been compared with excess volumes calculated from 'graph theory'.

IN continuation of our earlier studies^{1,2} on excess thermodynamic functions of binary non-electrolyte mixtures containing one of the components as an isomeric alkane, we report here the excess volumes of some binary systems of isooctane (2,2,4-trimethylpentane) with some aromatic compounds. The experimental results have been compared with the corresponding excess volumes calculated from graph theory^{3,4}.

Experimental

2,2,4-Trimethylpentane, benzene, toluene, *o*-xylene and *m*-xylene (each L.R. grade) were distilled over sodium metal. Chlorobenzene, benzaldehyde and acetophenone were distilled before use. The purity of these chemicals was checked by comparing their observed boiling points and densities with the corresponding literature values. The experimental details have been described elsewhere⁵.

Results and Discussion

Molar excess volumes (v^E) of the studied binary systems have been calculated using the relation,

$$v^E = (M_1x_1 + M_2x_2)/d - M_1x_1/d_1 - M_2x_2/d_2 \quad (1)$$

where, M_i , x_i and d_i denote molecular weight, mole fraction and density, respectively of the i th component ($i=1, 2$) and d is density of the mixture.

Excess volumes of the studied binary systems at rounded mole fractions alongwith the error in experimental v^E have been given in table 1. For the systems 2,2,4-trimethylpentane + benzene or + toluene, v^E values are symmetrical and positive throughout the studied composition range. The magnitude of excess volume for 2,2,4-trimethylpentane + benzene are higher than the corresponding values for n-octane + benzene system⁶. This may be explained in terms of comparatively less hindered interstitial accommodation within unlike molecules in case of the systems containing n-alkane than isomeric alkane.

The magnitude of excess volume decreases with the increase of number of substituted methyl groups on the benzene ring. This is evident from the excess volumes for the systems containing benzene, toluene, or a xylene as one of the components of the mixture (Fig. 1). For the systems containing

TABLE 1—MOLAR EXCESS VOLUME (v^E)* FOR BINARY SYSTEMS OF 2,2,4-TRIMETHYLPENTANE WITH SOME AROMATIC COMPOUNDS AT 40°

x_1	Benzene	Toluene	<i>o</i> -Xylene	<i>m</i> -Xylene	Chlorobenzene	Benzaldehyde	Acetophenone
0.1	0.18 (0.14)	0.13 (0.06)	-0.02	-0.18	-0.12 (-0.10)	-0.32 (-0.19)	-0.18 (-0.18)
0.2	0.26 (0.24)	0.19 (0.11)	-0.04	-0.21	-0.20 (-0.20)	-0.48 (-0.34)	-0.40 (-0.32)
0.3	0.34 (0.31)	0.22 (0.16)	-0.05	-0.22	-0.27 (-0.26)	-0.56 (-0.46)	-0.51 (-0.43)
0.4	0.39 (0.37)	0.23 (0.19)	-0.02	-0.19	-0.31 (-0.30)	-0.59 (-0.54)	-0.56 (-0.51)
0.5	0.41 (0.41)	0.21 (0.21)	0.00	0.00	-0.32 (-0.32)	-0.58 (-0.58)	-0.55 (-0.55)
0.6	0.37 (0.39)	0.19 (0.21)	0.01	0.16	-0.31 (-0.32)	-0.53 (-0.57)	-0.50 (-0.51)
0.7	0.30 (0.36)	0.16 (0.19)	0.02	0.19	-0.28 (-0.28)	-0.45 (-0.52)	-0.40 (-0.50)
0.8	0.22 (0.28)	0.11 (0.16)	0.01	0.15	-0.22 (-0.22)	-0.30 (-0.41)	-0.20 (-0.39)
0.9	0.13 (0.17)	0.06 (0.10)	0.01	0.09	-0.13 (-0.13)	-0.10 (-0.23)	-0.06 (-0.23)

*Error in experimental $v^E = \pm 0.02$ ml mol⁻¹; values in parentheses calculated from 'graph theory'.

Fig. 1. Plots of v^E vs mole fraction of 2,2,4-trimethylpentane (x_1) for some binary systems: 2,2,4-trimethylpentane + (Δ) benzene, (\circ) toluene, (\times) *o*-xylene, (\blacksquare) *m*-xylene, (\blacktriangle) chlorobenzene, (\bullet) benzaldehyde, (\square) acetophenone.

o- or *m*-xylene, the excess volume versus mole fraction plots are sigmoid with negative magnitude of v^E over the composition range rich in xylene component and positive values in the region rich in 2,2,4 trimethylpentane. In case of the binary systems containing chlorobenzene, benzaldehyde or acetophenone as a component the excess volumes are negative over the entire composition range. The negative values of excess volumes for the above systems may be due to the difference in the characteristic temperatures of the constituent components⁶, which lead to a negative free volume or equation-of-state term in v^E . It is interesting to note that the presence of both electron-releasing (*i.e.* CH_3) as well as electron-withdrawing (*i.e.* Cl, CHO, COCH_3) groups substituted on benzene ring produce a similar effect of decrease in excess volume in comparison to when the pure benzene is one of the components. However, this effect is more pronounced in case of the electron-withdrawing substituted group.

According to graph theory^{3,4} the excess volume may be calculated using the relation,

$$v^E = \alpha(1/(x_1, {}^3\xi_1 + x_2, {}^3\xi_2) - x_1/{}^3\xi_1 - x_2/{}^3\xi_2) \quad (2)$$

The connectivity parameters of third degree (${}^3\xi$) of component substances were calculated using the relation,

$${}^3\xi = \sum_{i < j} \sum_{j < k} \sum_{k < l} (\delta_i, \delta_j, \delta_k, \delta_l)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \quad (3)$$

$\delta_i, \delta_j, \delta_k$ etc. denote the degrees of i, j, k etc. vertices of the graph of a molecule. According to the basic assumption of this theory, $1/\xi^3$ of a molecule is a measure of the probability that its surface area interacts affectively with the corresponding surface area of other molecules. The values of ${}^3\xi$ for 2,2,4-trimethylpentane, benzene and toluene were 1.021, 1.500 and 1.894, respectively. For chlorobenzene, benzaldehyde and acetophenone, the values of ${}^3\xi$ used were the same as for benzene. The parameter α in equation (2) was calculated using experimental v^E at equimolar concentration of the mixture. The excess volumes calculated from graph theory for the systems: 2,2,4-trimethylpentane + benzene; + toluene; + chlorobenzene; + benzaldehyde; + acetophenone are given in parenthesis in Table 1. The calculated values of v^E agree fairly well with the experimental values for the systems containing benzene, toluene or chlorobenzene. In case of the systems containing benzaldehyde or acetophenone there is only a qualitative agreement between the theoretical and the experimental values. For the systems containing *o*- or *m*-xylene as one of the components, no comparison could be made between the calculated and the observed excess volumes owing to the apparent weakness of this theory that it can be applied to only such systems which exhibit either positive or negative values of v^E throughout the composition range of the mixture.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for providing financial help.

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